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IMAGE OF WOMEN IN MODERN LITERATURE AND APPROACHES TO THE ISSUE OF GENDER EQUALITY

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Abstract. The article analyzes the positive and negative interpretations of the image of a woman in Uzbek literature based on examples.

Key words: modern poetry, female image, mother image, women's rights, Mirtemir, A. Oripov, O. Hoshimov.

In Abdulla Qadiri's novel "The Past Days", O'tabboy's bird calls Kumush "an angel of salvation". Because she realized that her father-in-law's letter, which came into her hands, would play an important role in saving her father and husband from death, she delivered this letter to Khudoyor Khan's palace on time.

There are also works with a special attitude towards the image of talented, creative women. For example, Mirkarim Osim's works depict historical figures of creative women who left an important mark in our history. An example of this is the author's domestic work entitled "Mohlaroyim va Khanposhsha" about the famous Uzbek poet Nodirabegim.

Poems with the title "Woman" can be found in the works of most poets. Abdulla Oripov's poem "Ayol" is a vivid example of this.

Maxim Gorky, the leading representative of Russian literature of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, in his story "Mother's Ode" created in 1912, through the images of an Italian mother and the great world-loving entrepreneur Amir Temur, shows the great feeling of mother's love and great courage. that it is a force is especially noticeable with the mention of Amir Temur's respect for the female race of Nechog. In this work, translated by Zuhridin Isomiddinoy, and brought to Uzbek readers, Maxim Gorky, a child of a different country, a different age, a representative of a different religion, a different nation, expresses Amir Temur's respect for his mother as follows: "I, the servant of God, Temurbek my word! A woman is sitting next to me. Such women are wise, but she aroused feelings in my heart that were not even visible to me. He talks to me like he talks to his peers. After that, looking at her, I understood why she is not so afraid: she loves, because of the love in her tongue, she understands that her child is a spark of life, and from this spark, a fire will be

ignited for many centuries. After all, all the prophets were once children, and wrestlers were not a piece of meat in their time!"

Childbirth is one of the worst pains in the world, it is very difficult to leave a child alive. Uvaisi's life is an example of this.

O'tkir Hashimov's work "Works of the World" is an example of the Uzbek interpretation of Uzbek mothers in Uzbek literature. Such an example has the reflection of millions of Uzbek mothers. A living statue was placed in "World's affairs" to the mother of the Uzbek, who was a mushtipar, a mushfiq and a slob.

The image of the Mother discovered in "The World's Affairs" is embodied in the eyes of the reader in other times and other places in O'tkir Hashimov's later works. For example, Aunt Kurbanoi in "Dreams of Past Lives" in many ways logically continues the image of Oyi in the story. In the story "The Last Victim of the War", the modesty and modesty of Umri's mother are almost no different from the qualities of the mother in these two works.

O'. Hoshimov, in his journalistic article entitled "Ayol", compares Mother's creative ability to Kurrai soil and writes: "Perhaps, this is where the expressions motherland, motherland, and motherland came from. Perhaps this is where the expression mother-earth comes from. That's why I liken the globe to a woman."

There are many poets who glorified the woman as a mother. Examples of this are Mirtemir's "Onaginam" and Abdulla Oripov's "Onajon". In particular, Mirtemir praised Uzbek women in his poem "Toshbu" in a special way. The poet writes:

*Toshbu: Sensiz O'zbekiston – O'zbekistonmas,
Sensiz keng jahon ham sira jahonmas, Toshbu!*

Mirtemir also has poems dedicated to women, such as Patti and Norbuvi.

Mirtemir's poetry is full of new ideas and images. For example, in the poem "Sen-Ona", he approached the traditional theme from the point of view of wartime requirements and created a new image of mother. The poet found a deep poetic thought about mothers that has not been said, but should be said, and skillfully expressed it in poetic language. In the work, the author instilled the spirit of war into the content of the work, drawing the image of a mother who sent her children to war, wishing for a white path and victory, and bravely carrying the mountain of separation and emigration on her shoulders:

*Alisherga alla aytib uxlatgan,
Sen – Ona.
Tarobiyini og'ir janga jo'natgan
Sen – Ona.*

Olamni nurida munavvar yetgan

Sen – Ona...

In the poem "Hadisa" the poet created a glorious image of mother. He was praised by:

*Sen ezgu timsolday,
Tengsiz sohibjamolday
O'ylaganim kuylagan,
Chunki, axir, onasan,
Elimda durdonasan.*

In the poem "Onaginam", a product of the last period of Mirtemir's work, the child's undying love for his mother, sacred feelings about filial duty are depicted in a folk simple, deep, natural and attractive way. On this basis, the child's mental state and infinite harmony are masterfully embodied:

*Seni arzimas bir yumushingni ado etolmadim,
Seni bir ishorangga
Yuz umbaloq oshib ketolmaganim
Seni jindek xush vaqt qilgani,
Seni jindek xush vaqt qilgani
Tengsiz jarlardan o'tolmaganim
Tog'day zil,
Abadiyatday cheksiz
Armon bo'lib qoldi dilimda, onaginam.*

The poet's poems such as "Onaginam", "Sen – Ona", "Kultepa", "Ona bag'rin", "Men ketganda", "Hali ham", "Lolazor" perfectly expressed the image of mother created with high artistic skill..

In the poem "Onaginam":

***Suyaklarimni sirqiratib,
Och tevatday g'ajiguncha,
Ko'zimda yosh tirqiratib,
jig'ildonimda achchiq bo'zaday
achig'uvchi g'ashlik...*** says the poet.

Thus, Mirtemir was able to use the image of his mother among various images in poetry, and put important poetic thoughts into the lines of lyrics. He adapted them to the spirit of the times and sang them skillfully. Therefore, Mirtemir's poetry is full of emotions, passionate poetic thoughts, passionate, sincere and gentle lyrics, beautiful images and motifs. The image of the mother in the poet's

poetry rises to the level of the image of the homeland, the people, and gives certain ideas about the past and present of the Uzbek people.

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